

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

DEVELOPING EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN FUTURE LEADERS: TRAINING PROGRAM AND RESULTS

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Abstract

Thus, it can be concluded that as a result of the application of the EQ development program, the ability of leaders to accurately convey the emotional state non-verbally, as well as abilities such as the correct decoding of transmitted non-verbal information, the ability to see the variety and variability of other people's emotional state, etc. qualities have increased significantly.

Keywords: leader, management, emotional intelligence, self-awareness

Actuality of theme. In our rapidly developing era, it is one of important issues to identify the psychological problems that bother people and to find their solutions. Because this not only ensures the emotional well-being of a person but also prevents possible psychosomatic diseases. As it is known, several factors influence personality formation, among which emotional intelligence plays a big role. In 1995, D. Goleman published the book "Emotional Intelligence" and emphasized the importance of being able to reflect human emotions in his work correctly. In his book, he noted that emotional intelligence also refers to the ability to process and use emotional information correctly [3, p. 21].

It is known that the concept of emotional intelligence has become one of the most relevant issues of psychology since the beginning of the 20th century. Over the years, researchers have begun to study emotional intelligence, its structure and its components. The main goal of these studies was related to the extent to which a person can control his emotions, the successes achieved in the development of each personality, the desires and the decisions he makes.

As it is known, emotional intelligence (EQ) determines the emotional sensitivity and emotional expressiveness of both oneself and others, the ability to control emotions, allowing a person to understand and control other people as well as himself. From this point of view, the concept of emotional intelligence is of special importance in the field of studying the practical activity of managers. Because this is one of the important components of their work, and at the same time, it is the subject of this activity.

Even though the concept of EQ appeared in psychology relatively recently (less than 20 years ago), the study of EQ has become one of the most pressing problems of modern psychological theory and practice. Many works of local and foreign scientists are mainly devoted to the theoretical justification of the existence of this phenomenon, to the study of its structure and importance as a determinant of the successful activity of representatives of humanitarian professions, especially leaders, teachers and managers. At the same time, as a professionally important quality of managers, EQ

is not sufficiently studied and the possibility of its development as one of the factors in the formation of their professional competence in future managers remains open.

The aim of the study. The purpose of this article is to describe the results of a formative experiment on the development of emotional intelligence of future leaders with the help of specially organized social-psychological training.

EQ is a professionally important quality of a leader's personality that develops throughout life through mastering a person's emotional experience and needs to be purposefully formed in the process of professional training (to increase its level). As a theoretical and methodological basis for the construction of the EQ model during the study, we used the structural-integrative approach to the study of intelligence [5, p. 31].

M.A.Kholodnaya's concept is based on the category of mental experience presented in three main forms - mental structures, mental space and mental representation. We believe that the structural-integrative approach is the best and most multifaceted system for understanding the essence of intelligence. Based on this approach, it is possible to build a clear and complete model of EQ. We consider EQ in the structure of general intelligence and understand it as a special form of organization of individual emotional experience in the form of (a) existing emotional structures, (b) emotional reflection space created by them, and (3) emotional experience (Zhuravlyova, 2009). For the development of EQ, in our opinion, group work, psychotherapy and art therapy methods can be used.

Social-psychological training program for the development of EQ

To study the possibilities of developing the EQ of future leaders, we developed a social-psychological training program, the tasks of which were: 1) to expand the boundaries of the emotional experience of future leaders; 2) promote awareness of this experience, their emotional potential;

3) stimulation of the positive orientation of the search activity within the framework of emotional experience; 4) acquiring knowledge about other people's

emotional experience (experience sharing); 5) acquisition of skills to activate one's own emotional experience, opportunities to use it to stimulate mental processes (one's own and others) and mentality in general;

6) to achieve emotional catharsis, and release from emotional clamps.

The training program includes a) theoretical material on emotions and EQ problems; b) tasks and exercises selected by us during the study of modern training for the development of emotions, training for the development of personal development and gardening skills, actual training for the development of EQ; c) Exercises specially designed by us according to the proposed business model of EQ.

The training form of the developing program was selected based on the following provisions.

First, as noted by I.V. Vachkov (1999), training orientation is secondary in most cases, and in some cases, the cognitive component may be completely absent, while emotional experience plays a leading role. That is, participation in any kind of training will contribute to the development of emotional experience and, as a result, human EI. Therefore, the choice of this particular type of developmental influence became the most adequate according to the goals of the formative experiment [9].

Second, training as a form of group work is, in our opinion, more compatible with a facilitative approach. Based on this, we understand training as a method of creation, which needs to be developed and self-actualized in order to solve the psychological problems and limitations of group members.

The research experiment was conducted on executives, with 30 experimental people and 30 control groups.

The following methods were used to diagnose the development level of EQ before and after training: N. Hall's EQ evaluation method; survey "EmIn" D.V. Lucina (2006); methodology of communicative tolerance; The selection of these methods is due to the fact that their scale reflects the development levels of individual emotional abilities, which we consider as indicators of the development of EQ according to the structural-integrative concept.

In order to determine the reliability of the described diagnostic tool, a correlation analysis was performed in the SPSS program. Spearman's correlation coefficient was used to test internal reliability. Statistically significant relationships ($p < 0.01$) were found between the combined scales for the diagnosis of individual components of EQ. Spearman's correlation coefficient was also used to determine external reliability, as a result of which a correlation was found between total EQ and EQ indicators by D. Lyucin's method and N. Hall's method ($p < 0.01$).

Diagnostic results were evaluated according to three levels of EQ development.

1. A low level of EQ development is characteristic of people who cannot productively use their own emotional experience and can't see and understand other people's emotional states. Such people do not analyze the feelings and behaviour of other people, they are not

able to think about their own feelings and emotions. Because they do not have the necessary skills, emotional abilities, or attention. They prefer not to see other people's emotional experiences. When others show strong emotions when they feel discomfort when they don't know how to react in such a situation, they can behave inappropriately (for example, they get angry and angry when they see tears), they can show impoliteness, and sarcasm in inappropriate situations [4, 15]. They have little control over their emotions in everyday life and can show their emotions in inappropriate situations. When emotional situations arise that are out of the ordinary, they can lose self-control and allow emotions to dominate the mind, resulting in emotional, impulsive, irrational actions.

2. Average level of EQ development. In interpersonal relationships, such people are more inclined to judge others by their actions than to trust their feelings. To a certain extent, they can feel the mood of other people and manage the situation on this basis, but they are not inclined to use these abilities more often, they regulate their relations with other people more according to the principles of compatibility. social and moral standards [10]. Such people are characterized by normative thinking, adherence to rules, and a low level of creativity. Affected by emotional relationships. Thinking about feelings is quite formal, that is, when they discuss their feelings, they rely on generally accepted formulas rather than being aware of their feelings. In everyday life, they successfully control their emotions, but when situations arise that are out of the ordinary, they can lose control of themselves for a short time [2, p. 11].

3. High level of EQ development. Such people are prone to self-analysis of emotions and experiences, as well as to the analysis of the feelings and behaviour of other people. They pay strong attention to people, show interest in them, their feelings, experiences, and behaviour, are closely interested in the inner world of others, are sociable, sociable, and choose professions of the "person-to-person" type. They can sensitively feel and understand the emotions of other people. They can decipher facial and kinesthetic expressions of emotions with high accuracy. On the one hand, they can adequately express their feelings, and on the other hand, they can manage them successfully. They do not allow the negative influence of emotions on the process of communication and interaction with other people. They have strong charisma. The ability to emotionally influence other people, to inspire others, to lead. Tcany stimulates mental processes through emotions. A high level of EQ development is necessary for the successful professional activity of an experienced manager.

Conclusion

The obtained results show that it is possible to increase the level of professional competence of future managers through the purposeful development of EI with the help of specially organized training included in the professional training process. In addition, the results of the formative experiment demonstrate the practical need for a longitudinal study of the dynamics of EQ development by future managers and professionals of this profession. It is likely that the development of

EQ components will not be linear, but will occur in stages, with the manifestation of dominant developmental components at each stage. Such dynamics, in which the expansion of emotional experience under the influence of social-psychological training leads to a decrease in emotion management, could explain the obtained results.

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